

Diabetic Ketoacidosis and Its Outcome in Children

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The idea of this study was to determine the clinical profile, demographic data and outcome of diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) in children of age less than 18 years diagnosed with T1DM.

Materials and Methods: Clinical presentation, demographic features, clinical presentation and laboratory findings for all the patients suffering from T1DM with DKA, were observed. Patients admitted were of age less than 18.

Results: A total of 60 children of T1DM with DKA were examined. Mean age of cases was 8.9 years with standard deviation of 1.7 years. There were 32 (53.3%) patients between 10 to 18 years of age while 28 (46.6%) were less than 10 years of age. Out of which 20 (33.3%) were male and 40 (66.6%) females. 42 (70%) patients belonged to urban areas and 18 (30%) lived in rural areas. A total of 30 (50%) cases were newly diagnosed with T1DM. Prominent symptoms recorded at the time of hospitalization were polyuria 48 (80%) and polydipsia 42 (70%). Mean blood glucose at the time of admission was 407.35 mg/dl. Recovery time was 22.3 hours. Frequent complications were hypokalemia 22 (36.6%) and hypernatremia 18 (30%).

Conclusions: It's crucial to make a diagnosis of T1DM earlier to prevent DKA and its complications.

Keywords: Type 1 diabetes mellitus, ketoacidosis, diabetic ketoacidosis

INTRODUCTION

A rise in prevalence of Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) among children has been recorded in recent times. Middle income countries like Pakistan are at greater risk by Diabetes. Diabetic Ketoacidosis (DKA) is a severe complication caused by diabetes, especially T1DM (Bhardwaj, Yadav & Sharma 2017).

Each year Prevalence of DKA is increasing by 3%. Among children, the diagnosis method DKA is determined by "International Society for Pediatric and Adolescent Diabetes (ISPAD)" in year 2018, venous pH less than 7.3, as blood glucose more

than 11 mmol/L (approx. 198 mg/dL) or bicarbonate less than 15 mmol/L and Ketonemia or ketonuria (Bhardwaj, Yadav & Sharma 2017). There are three categories for DKA i.e mild, medium, severe. Complications of DKA are not treated seriously, even though there has been a rise in T1DM incidence (Naeem 2017).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted on patients less than 18 years of age, diagnosed with T1DM with DKA presented to Pediatrics unit 2 of Samnabad Hospital, Lahore March 1, 2018 to March 1, 2019.

Parents/guardians who refused to give consent were not included in the case study. Laboratory examinations and clinical assessments like blood glucose, urine ketones, serum electrolytes, serum creatinine and serum electrolytes were carried out. DKA was labeled as blood glucose >200 mg/dL, pH less than 7.3, bicarbonate less than 15 mmol/L and ketonuria. Resolution of DKA was categorized based on venous blood pH or bicarbonate levels as: Mild DKA: Venous blood pH between 7.21 to 7.30 or bicarbonate level between 10 mmol/L to 15 mmol/L. Moderate DKA: Venous blood pH between 7.11 to 7.20 or bicarbonate level between 5 mmol/L to 10 mmol/L. Severe DKA: Venous blood pH < 7.10 or bicarbonate level < 145 mEq/l respectively whereas hypokalemia and hyperkalemia was declared with serum potassium < 3.5 mEq/l and > 5 mEq/l respectively. Post initial improvement, there was a dilapidation in neurological function that led to the diagnosis of cerebral edema. Serum creatinine level higher than 1.5 mg/dL was considered alarming. For analysis and data entry, SPSS version 20.0 was used. Frequencies were calculated for qualitative variables

RESULTS

A total of 60 children of T1DM with DKA were examined. Mean age of cases was 8.9 years with standard deviation of 1.7 years. There were 32

(53.3%) patients between 10 to 18 years of age while 28 (46.6%) were less than 10 years of age. Out of which 20 (33.3%) were male and 40 (66.6%) females. 42 (70%) patients belonged to urban areas and 18 (30%) lived in rural areas. A total of 30 (50%) cases were newly diagnosed with T1DM. Prominent symptoms recorded at the time of hospitalization were polyuria 48 (80%) and polydipsia 42 (70%). Mean blood glucose at the time of admission was 407.35 mg/dl. Recovery time was 22.3 hours. Frequent complications were hypokalemia 22 (36.6%) and hypernatremia 18 (30%).

DISCUSSION

DKA is considered as a major causes of mortality amongst T1DM. Mean age of cases in study was 8.9 years and 53.3% aged between 10 to 18 years. An analysis carried out in Saudia Arabia is comparable to our report which states the mean age of 11 years. Pulungan et al (2018) and other authors discovered that rate of prevalence is higher in females which could be attributed to hormonal

changes.e.g growth hormone and estrogen for instance. 70% of the patients were from urban area. Higher rate of mortality in cases of TD1M is due to late diagnosis. Prominent symptoms of DKA are polyuria and polydipsia, vomiting and altered level of consciousness. Study revealed respiratory distress in 23% cases while it was 58.6%-87.1% in other observations. Severe DKA transpired to be most common type. Common complications were Hypokalemia and Hyponatraemia.

The frequency of cerebral edema was a fluctuating in various observations. We discovered cerebral edema in 7.5%. Cases that succumbed to death during our study were recently diagnosed with deranged serum creatinine. We discovered serum creatinine level in 6% patients. We are confident that our study will help broaden the insight about the case profile of DKA in our area.

CONCLUSION

Diagnosis of T1DM shouldn't be underestimated, as to a avoid incidence of DKA along with its complications.

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